

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11120495>

ANIQ INTEGRALNI BA'ZI BIR TADBICHLARI

Mamasidiqov Baxodir Qobuljon o'g'li
Andijan Institute of Mechanical Engineering

***Annotatsiya:** Bu maqolada aniq integralning ba'zi amaliy va nazariy tadbicHLari ko'rib chiqiladi. Aniq integralning matematik formulalar yordamida qanday hisoblanishga doir ba'zi misollar ko'rib chiqildi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** Aniq integralni ta'rifi va unga oid misollar, egri chiziqli trapetsiya yuzini hisoblash, qutb koordinatalar sistemasida berilga figurani yuzini hisoblash ko'rib chiqildi.*

SOME APPLICATIONS OF THE DEFINITE INTEGRAL

***Annotation:** This article reviews some practical and theoretical applications of the definite integral. Some examples of how to calculate the definite integral using mathematical formulas were considered.*

***Keywords:** Definition of definite integral and related examples, calculation of the surface of a curved trapezoid, calculation of the surface of a given figure in the polar coordinate system was considered.*

Ma'lumki, bugungi kunda umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari va akademik litseylarda o'rganila boshlangan integral tushunchasi oliy o'quv yurtlarida davom ettirilmoqda.

Integral hisob matematik analizning integrallar, ularning xossalari, hisoblash usullari va tadbicHLarini o'rganadigan bo'limidir.

Integral hisob tabiatshunoslik va matematikaning juda kop masalalarini o'rganish zaruriyati tufayli paydo bo'lgan. Bulardan eng muhimlari-harakatning ma'lum, ammo uzgaruvchi tezligiga asosan berilgan vaqt oraligida otilgan yolni aniqlashga oid fizik masala va geometrik figuralarning yuzalari, hajmlari, ekstriumga oid geometrik masalalar va hokazo masalalar shular jumlasidandir.

Integral hisobning asosiy tushunchasi-integral bo'lib u mos ravishda aniqmas va aniq integrallarga bo'linadi. Bu integrallar talabalar keyinchalik o'rganadigan karrali, egri chiziqli va sirt integrallarini puxta o'zlashtirishlarida muhim o'rin tutadi. Bu integrallarni har birini kiritishga amaliyotning u yoki bu masalasi turtki bo'lganligini

ta'kidlash va ularni o'rganish sirt integrallarini o'rganish bilan yakunlanishini takidlash kerak. Sirt integrallarni hisoblash asosan uni ikki va uch o'lchovli integrallarni hisoblashga keltirishga asoslanadi. Quyida ularni keltiramiz

Agar $[a, b]$ kesmada funksiya $f(x) \geq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda $y = f(x)$ egri chiziq, OX o'qi va $x=a$ hamda $x=b$ to'g'ri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan egri chizikli trapetsiyaning yuzi

$$S = \int_a^b f(x) dx$$

(1)

ga teng bo'ladi. Agar $[a, b]$ kesmada $f(x) \leq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda aniq integral $\int_a^b f(x) dx \leq 0$ bo'ladi.

Absolyut qiymatiga ko'ra bu integralning qiymati ham tegishli egri chizikli trapetsiyaning yuziga teng:

$$S = \int_a^b |f(x)| dx$$

(1')

Agar $f(x)$ funksiya $[a, b]$ kesmada ishorasini chekli son marta o'zgartirsa, u holda integralni butun $[a, b]$ kesmada qisman kesmachalar bo'yicha integrallar yig'indisiga ajratamiz. $f(x) > 0$ bo'lgan kesmalarda integral musbat, $f(x) < 0$ bo'lgan kesmalarda integral manfiy bo'ladi. Butun kesma bo'yicha olingan integral OX o'qidan yuqorida va pastda yotuvchi yuzlarning tegishli algebraik yig'indisini beradi (1-rasm). Yuzlar yig'indisini odatdagi ma'noda hosil qilish uchun yuqorida ko'rsatilgan kesmalar bo'yicha olingan integrallar absolyut qiymatlari yig'indisini topish yoki

$$S = \int_a^b |f(x)| dx \quad (1'')$$

integralni hisoblash kerak.

b) Agar $y_1 = f_1(x)$ va $y_2 = f_2(x)$ egri chiziqlar hamda $x=a$ va $x=b$ to'g'ri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan figuraning yuzini hisoblash kerak bo'lsa, u holda $f_1(x) \geq f_2(x)$ shart bajarilganda figuraning yuzi quyidagiga teng:

$$S = \int_a^b (f_1(x) - f_2(x)) dx$$

1-misol. $y = \cos x$, $y = 0$ chiziqlar bilan figuraning yuzi hisoblansin, bunda $x \in [0, 2\pi]$.

Yechish. $x \in \left[0, \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ va $x \in \left[\frac{3\pi}{2}, 2\pi\right]$ da $\cos x \geq 0$ hamda $x \in \left[\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{2}\right]$ da $\cos x \leq 0$

bo'lgani uchun

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \int_0^{2\pi} |\cos x| dx = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cos x dx + \left| \int_{\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{3\pi}{2}} (-\cos x) dx \right| + \int_{\frac{3\pi}{2}}^{2\pi} \cos x dx = \\ &= \sin x \Big|_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} + \left| \sin x \Big|_{\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{3\pi}{2}} \right| + \sin x \Big|_{\frac{3\pi}{2}}^{2\pi} \\ &= \sin \frac{\pi}{2} - \sin 0 + \left| \sin \frac{3\pi}{2} - \sin \frac{\pi}{2} \right| + \sin 2\pi - \sin \frac{3\pi}{2} = \\ &= 1 + |-1 - 1| - (-1) = 4 \end{aligned}$$

Demak, $S=4$ (kv.birlik)

2-misol. $y = x^2 + 1$ va $y = 3 - x$ chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan figuraning yuzini hisoblang.

Yechish. Figurani yasash uchun avval ushbu $\begin{cases} y = x^2 + 1 \\ y = 3 - x \end{cases}$ sistemani yechib, chiziqlarning kesishish nuqtalarini topamiz.

Bu chiziqlar $A(-2; 5)$ va $B(1; 2)$ nuqtalarda kesishadi. U holda

$$S = \int_{-2}^1 (3 - x) dx - \int_{-2}^1 (x^2 + 1) dx = \int_{-2}^1 (2 - x - x^2) dx = \left(2x - \frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_{-2}^1$$

$$=$$

$$= \left(2 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3} \right) - \left(-4 - \frac{4}{2} + \frac{8}{3} \right) = \frac{9}{2} (\text{kv. birl.})$$

b) Agar egri chiziqli trapetsiyaning yuzi $x = \phi(t), y = \psi(t)$ tenglamalari parametrik shaklda berilgan chiziq bilan chegaralangan bo'lsa, bunda bu tenglamalar $[a, b]$ kesmadagi biror $y = f(x)$ funksiyani aniqlaydi, bunda $t \in [\alpha, \beta]$ va $\phi(\alpha) = a, \phi(\beta) = b$.

U holda egri chiziqli trapetsiyaning yuzi $S = \int_a^b y dx$ formula bo'yicha hisoblanishi mumkin bo'ladi. Bu integralda o'zgaruvchini almashtiramiz:

$$x = \phi(t), dx = \phi'(t) dt$$

$$y = f(x) = f(\phi(t)) = \psi(t)$$

Demak,

$$S = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \psi(t) \phi'(t) dt$$

(3)

Bu formula chiziq parametrik tenglamalar bilan berilganda egri chiziqli trapetsiyaning yuzini hisoblash formulasidir.

3-misol. $x = a \cos t, y = b \sin t$ ellips bilan chegaralangan sohaning yuzi hisoblansin.

Yechish. Ellipsning yuqori yarim yuzini hisoblab, uni 2 ga ko'paytiramiz.

$-a \leq x \leq +a$ uchun

$$-a = a \cos t, \cos t = -1, t = \pi$$

$$a = a \cos t, \cos t = 1, t = 0$$

$$S = 2 \int_{\pi}^0 b \sin t (-a \sin t dt) = -2ab \int_{\pi}^0 \sin^2 t dt = \pi ab.$$

AB egri chiziq qutb koordinatalarida $\rho = f(\theta)$ formula bilan berilgan va $f(\theta)$ funksiya $[\alpha, \beta]$ kesmada uzluksiz bo'lsin.

Ushbu $\rho = f(\theta)$ egri chiziq va qutb o'qlari bilan α va β burchak hosil qiluvchi 2 ta $\phi = \alpha, \phi = \beta$ nurlar bilan n ta ixtiyoriy qismlarga bo'lamiz. O'tkazilgan nurlar orasidagi burchaklarni $\Delta\theta_1, \Delta\theta_2, \dots, \Delta\theta_n$ bilan belgilaymiz.

θ_{i-1} bilan θ_i orasidagi biror $\bar{\theta}_i$ burchakka mos nurning uzunligini $\bar{\rho}_i$ orqali belgilaymiz. Radiusi $\bar{\rho}_i$ va markaziy burchagi $\Delta\theta_i$ bo'lgan doiraviy sektorni qaraymiz. Uning yuzi $\Delta S_i = \frac{1}{2} \bar{\rho}_i^2 \Delta\theta_i$ ga teng bo'ladi.

Ushbu yig'indi

$$S_n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{\rho}_i^2 \Delta\theta_i = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n [f(\bar{\theta}_i)]^2 \Delta\theta_i$$

zinapoyasimon sektorning yuzini beradi.

Bu yig'indi $\alpha \leq \theta \leq \beta$ kesmada $\rho^2 = |f(\theta)|^2$ funksiyaning integral yig'indisi bo'lgani sababli uning limiti $\max \Delta\theta_i \rightarrow 0$ da $\frac{1}{2} \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \rho^2 d\theta$ aniq integralga teng. Bu $\Delta\theta_i$ burchak ichida qanday ρ_i nur olishimizga bog'liq emas. Demak, OAB sektorning yuzi:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \rho^2 d\theta = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} [f(\theta)]^2 d\theta$$

4-misol. $\rho = a(1 + \cos \theta)$, $a > 0$ kardioida bilan chegaralangan figuraning yuzini hisoblang.

$$S = 2S_1 = 2 \frac{1}{2} \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \rho^2 d\theta = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \rho^2 d\theta$$

$$S = \int_0^{\pi} a^2 (1 + \cos \theta)^2 d\theta = a^2 \int_0^{\pi} (1 + 2 \cos \theta + \cos^2 \theta) d\theta =$$

$$= a^2 \int_0^{\pi} \left(\frac{3}{2} + 2 \cos \theta + \frac{1}{2} \cos 2\theta \right) d\theta = a^2 \left(\frac{3}{2} \theta + 2 \sin \theta + \frac{1}{4} \sin 4\theta \right) \Big|_0^{\pi} =$$

$$= \frac{3}{2} \pi a^2; S = \frac{3}{2} \pi a^2 (\text{kv. birlik})$$

Tekislikda to'g'ri burchakli koordinatalar sistemasida egri chiziq $y = f(x)$ tenglama bilan berilgan bo'lsin.

Bu egri chiziqning $x=a$ va $x=b$ vertikal to'g'ri chiziqlar orasidagi AB yoyining uzunligini topamiz.

AB yoyda absissalari $a = x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n = b$ bo'lgan $A, M_1, M_2, \dots, M_i, \dots, B$ nuqtalarni olamiz va $AM_1, M_1, M_2, \dots, M_{n-1}M_n =$

$A + B$ vatarlarni o'tkazamiz, ularning uzunliklarini mos ravishda $\Delta S_1, \Delta S_2, \dots, \Delta S_n$ bilan belgilaymiz. AB yoy ichiga chizilgan siniq chiziqning uzunligi

$S_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta S_i$ bo'lgani uchun AB yoyning uzunligi

$$S = \lim_{\max \Delta S_i \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta S_i \quad (4)$$

bo'ladi.

Faraz qilaylik, $f(x)$ funksiya va uning $f'(x)$ hosilasi $[a, b]$ kesmada uzluksiz bo'lsin. U holda

$$\Delta S_i = \sqrt{(\Delta x_i)^2 + (\Delta y_i)^2} = \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\Delta y_i}{\Delta x_i}\right)^2} \cdot \Delta x_i$$

yoki Lagranj teoremasiga asosan

$$\frac{\Delta y_i}{\Delta x_i} = \frac{f(x_i) - f(x_{i-1})}{x_i - x_{i-1}} = f'(\xi) \quad \text{bunda} \quad x_{i-1} < \xi < x_i \quad \text{bo'lgani uchun} \quad \Delta S_i = \sqrt{1 + (f'(\xi))^2} \Delta x_i \text{ bo'ladi.}$$

Ichki chizilgan siniq chiziqning uzunligi esa

$$\Delta S_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{1 + (f'(\xi))^2} \Delta x_i$$

Shartga ko'ra $f'(x)$ funksiya uzluksiz, demak, $\sqrt{1 + (f'(x))^2}$ funksiya ham uzluksizdir. Shuning uchun integral yig'indining limiti mavjud va u quyidagi aniq integralga teng:

$$S = \lim_{\max \Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{1 + (f'(\xi))^2} \Delta x_i = \int_a^b \sqrt{1 + (f'(\xi))^2} dx$$

Demak, yoy uzunligini hisoblash formulasi:

$$S = \int_a^b \sqrt{1 + (f'(x))^2} dx = \int_a^b \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2} dx \quad (5)$$

ekan. Endi egri chiziq tenglamasi

$$x = \phi(t), y = \psi(t), \alpha \leq t \leq \beta \quad (6)$$

parametrik ko'rinishda berilgan bo'lsin, bunda $\phi(t)$ va $\psi(t)$ uzluksiz hosilali uzluksiz funksiyalar va $\phi'(t)$ berilgan oraliqda nolga aylanmaydi.

Bu holda (6) tenglama biror $y = f(x)$ funksiyani aniqlaydi. Bu funksiya uzluksiz bo'lib $\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{\psi'(t)}{\phi'(t)}$ uzluksiz hosilaga ega. $a = \phi(\alpha), b = \phi(\beta)$ bo'lsin. (5) integralda $x = \phi(t), dx = \phi'(t)dt$ almashtirish bajaramiz. U holda

$$S = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\psi'(t)}{\phi'(t)}\right)^2} \cdot \phi'(t) dt \text{ yoki}$$

$$S = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \sqrt{(\phi'(t))^2 + (\psi'(t))^2} dt$$

(7)

Agar egri chiziq fazoda

$$x = \phi(t), y = \psi(t), z = \chi(t)$$

(8)

parametrik tenglamalar bilan berilgan va $\phi(t)$, $\psi(t)$, $\chi(t)$ funksiyalar $[a, b]$ kesmada uzluksiz hamda uzluksiz hosilalarga ega bo'lsa, egri chiziq aniq limitlarga ega bo'ladi va u

$$S = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \sqrt{(\phi'(t))^2 + (\psi'(t))^2 + (\chi'(t))^2} dt$$

(9)

formula bilan aniqlanadi.

Qutb koordinatalar sistemasida egri chiziqning tenglamasi

$$\rho = f(\theta) \tag{10}$$

bo'lsin. Qutb koordinatalaridan Dekart koordinatalariga o'tish formulasi: $x = \rho \cos \theta$, $y = \rho \sin \theta$ yoki (10) dan foydalansak:

$$x = f(\theta) \cos \theta, y = f(\theta) \sin \theta$$

Bu tenglamalarga egri chiziqning parametrik tenglamalari deb qarab, yoy uzunligini hisoblash uchun (7) formulani tadbqiq qilamiz.

$$\frac{dx}{d\theta} = f'(\theta) \cos \theta - f(\theta) \sin \theta \quad \theta, \frac{dy}{d\theta} = f'(\theta) \sin \theta + f(\theta) \cos \theta$$

U holda

$$\left(\frac{d\vec{r}}{d\theta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dy}{d\theta}\right)^2 = (f'(\theta))^2 + (f(\theta))^2 = \rho'^2 + \rho^2$$

Demak,

$$S = \int_{\theta_2}^{\theta_1} \sqrt{\rho'^2 + \rho^2} d\theta \tag{11}$$

Misollar.

1) $x^2 + y^2 = r^2$ aylana uzunligi hisoblansin.

Yechish. Dastlab aylananing 1-kvadrantda yotgan to'rttdan bir qismining uzunligini hisoblaymiz. U holda AB yoyning tenglamasi

$$y = \sqrt{r^2 - x^2}, \frac{dy}{dx} = -\frac{x}{\sqrt{r^2 - x^2}};$$

$$\frac{1}{4}S = \int_0^r \sqrt{1 + \frac{x^2}{r^2 - x^2}} dx = \int_0^r \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 - x^2}} dx = r \cdot \arcsin \frac{x}{r} \Big|_0^r = r \cdot \frac{\pi}{2}$$

Butun aylananing uzunligi: $S = 2\pi r$.

2) $\rho = a(1 + \cos \theta)$ kardioidaning uzunligi topilsin. Kardioida qutb o'qiga nisbatan simmetrikdir. θ qutb burchagini 0 dan π gacha o'zgartirib, izlanayotgan uzunlikning yarmini topamiz (5-rasm). (11) formuladan foydalanamiz, bunda

$$\begin{aligned} \rho' &= -a \sin \theta \\ S &= 2 \cdot \int_0^\pi \sqrt{a^2(1 + \cos \theta)^2 + a^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta = 2a\sqrt{2 + 2 \cos \theta} d\theta = \\ &= 4a \cdot \int_0^\pi \cos \frac{\theta}{2} = 8a \cdot \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \Big|_0^\pi = 8a \cdot 1 = 8a \end{aligned}$$

3) $x = a \cos t, y = b \sin t, 0 \leq t \leq 2\pi$ ellipsning uzunligi hisoblansin, bunda $a > b$.

Yechish. (4) formuladan foydalanamiz. Avval yoy uzunligining 1/4 qismini hisoblaymiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{S}{4} &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{a^2 \sin^2 t + b^2 \cos^2 t} dt = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{a^2(1 - \cos^2 t) + b^2 \cos^2 t} dt \\ &= \\ &= \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{a^2 - (a^2 - b^2) \cos^2 t} dt = a \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - \frac{a^2 - b^2}{a^2} \cos^2 t} dt = \\ &= a \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - k^2 \cos^2 t} dt \end{aligned}$$

bunda $k = \frac{\sqrt{a^2 - b^2}}{a} < 1$.

Demak, $S = 4a \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sqrt{1 - k^2 \cos^2 t} dt$.

Biror T jism berilgan bo'lsin. Bu jismni OX o'qqa perpendikulyar tekislik bilan kesishdan hosil bo'lgan har qanday kesimning yuzi ma'lum deb faraz qilamiz. Bu holda yuza kesuvchi tekislikning vaziyatiga bog'liq, ya'ni x ning funksiyasi bo'ladi:

$Q(x)$ ni uzluksiz funksiya deb faraz qilib, berilgan jism hajmini aniqlaymiz. $x = x_0 = a, x = x_1, x = x_2, \dots, x = x_n = b$ tekisliklarni o'tkazamiz. Har bir $x_{i-1} \leq x \leq x_i$ qismaniy oraliqda ixtiyoriy ξ_i nuqta tanlab olamiz va i ning har bir qiymati uchun yasovchisi x lar o'qiga parallel bo'lib, yo'naltiruvchisi T jismni $x = \xi_i$ tekislik bilan kesishdan hosil bo'lgan kesimning konturidan iborat bo'lgan silindrik jism yasaymiz. Asosining yuzi $Q(\xi_i)$ va balandligi Δx_i bo'lgan bunday elementar silindrning hajmi $Q(\xi_i)\Delta x_i$ ga teng. Hamma silindrlarning hajmi $v_n = \sum_{i=1}^n Q(\xi_i)\Delta x_i$ bo'ladi. Bu yig'indining $\max \Delta x_i \rightarrow 0$ dagi limiti berilgan **jismning hajmi** deyiladi:

$$v_n = \lim_{\max \Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^n Q(\xi_i)\Delta x_i$$

v_n miqdor $[a, b]$ kesmada uzluksiz $Q(x)$ funksiyaning integral yig'indisidir, shuning uchun limit mavjud va u

$$v = \int_a^b Q(x) dx$$

(12)

aniq integral bilan ifodalanadi.

Misol. $\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} + \frac{z^2}{c^2} = 1$ ellipsoidning hajmi hisoblanin.

Yechish. Ellipsoidni OYZ tekislikka parallel bo'lib undan x masofa uzoqlikdan o'tgan tekislik bilan kesganda yarim o'qlari

$$b_1 = b\sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}; c_1 = c\sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}} \text{ bo'lgan}$$

$$\frac{y^2}{\left(b\sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}\right)^2} + \frac{z^2}{\left(c\sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}\right)^2} = 1 \text{ ellips hosil bo'ladi.}$$

Bu ellipsning yuzi: $Q(x) = \pi b_1 c_1 = \pi bc \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}\right)$

Ellipsoidning hajmi:

$$v = \pi bc \int_{-a}^a \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}\right) dx = \pi bc \left(x - \frac{x^3}{3a^2}\right) \Big|_{-a}^a = \frac{4}{3} \pi abc (\text{kubbirl.})$$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR.

1. Safaeva Q., Shomansurova D. "Iqtisodiyotda matematika" Toshkent 2010
2. Sytsaeter Kn., Hammond P., Strom A. Essential Mathematics for Economic Analysis. Pearson Education Limited. London, New York 2014
3. Piskunov N.S. Differentsial va integral hisobi. I – II tomlar. -Toshkent: O'qituvchi, 1974.
4. Alimov.Sh, Ashurov R. Matematik analiz, 1-2-qismlar, Toshkent: Mumtoz so'z 2018.
5. Zulfixarov I.M, Mamasidikov B.Q Sun'iy intellektni yaratishda bul algebrasining mantiqiy yo'nalishdagi matematik taxlili// "Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya resurslaridan foydalanishning dolzarb muammolari, energiya tejamkor qurilmalarning samaradorligini oshirishda sun'iy intellekt va raqamli texnologiyalarni tadbiq etish" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-texnik anjuman 18-19.09 2023 pp. 346-348
6. Mamasidikov B.Q Talabalarda oliy matematika fanini o'qitishda determinant va uning yechilish usullarini o'rgatish // "Mexatronika va robotatexnika: muammolar rivojlantirish istiqbollari" mavzusidagi II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman <http://michascience.com/index.php/fji> 03.10 2023 pp 465-474
7. Mamasidikov B.Q Yuqori tartibli determinantni hisoblashni qulay usullari "Science and Education" scientific journal / www.openscience.uz Oktober 2023 / volume 4 ISSUE 10. 8-13
8. Mamasidikov B.Q Talabalarda kompleks o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarning integrali va uni hisoblash usullarini shakllantirish// "Axborot oqimlari va ntellektual tizimlarning ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy va texnik-texnologik tarmoqlardagi o'rni" mavzusida xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Andijon 10.11 2023 pp 284-288
9. Mamasidikov B.Q Uchinchi darajali tenglamalarni yechishda talabalarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish // "Axborot oqimlari va ntellektual tizimlarning ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy va texnik-texnologik tarmoqlardagi o'rni" mavzusida xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Andijon 10.11 2023 pp 289-294